

ISic0330

Funerary inscription for Aphrodito, a mime actress

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.03.20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Found c.1731 in the foundations of the Church of S.Caterina da Siena
(known as S. Caterina del Rosario), previously attached to the

convent of the Dominican

Fathers, today seat of the Archivio di Stato, at via S.Agata 2.

Coordinates

37.503059, 15.088940

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 390

Physical Description

A white marble plaque, apparently complete: the upper and lower edges are regular, the left and right sides irregular. The rear is finished and smooth.

Dimensions

Height 29 cm

Width 33.5 cm

Depth 2.1 cm

Layout

Latin text over six lines, roughly centred on the plaque. Lines

1-3 are more widely spaced and better centred; lines 4-6 are more compressed in the lower right.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letters show some tendency to a cursive style, but the name in line 2

is notably marked out in a more classical majuscule style.

One instance of ligature

in line 6. Use of simple hedera as interpuncts in lines 3-6.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-6: 15-22 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not measured mm

Text

1. D (is) M (anibus) s (acrum)

2. Aphrodito
3. mimas vix (it)
4. ann (is) XXXX
5. Eutyclus con
6. iugi meren t̂i f (ecit)

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Aphrodito the mime lived for 40 years. Eutyclus (set this up) for his deserving wife.

Translation (it)

Consacrato agli Dei Mani. La mima Aphrodito visse 40 anni. Eutyclus (lo costruì) per la meritevole moglie.

Commentary

Aphrodito [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/id/V3a-37802>] is a rare female name, most commonly found in northern Greece / Macedonia. Mimas copies the Greek word μῦμας designating a mime actor. Mime, a highly successful form of popular, comic drama, had its first real success in fifth-century BC Sicily, and was very popular in Rome and Italy throughout the later Republic and Imperial period. Ancient mime has however only come down to us in fragments. The genre flourished in the Hellenistic east also, and Aphrodito's name suggests that she may have come from the eastern Mediterranean to practice her art in Sicily and Italy.

For online Italian edition see EpiCUM420 [http://epicum.istc.cnr.it/EPICUM/?page_id=1636]

Digital identifiers:

EpiCUM Ursino420

TM 491539

EDR 139551

EDCS 21900368

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0330>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4022612

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae*

Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7046 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650759>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 51

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 59

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0330. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335133>

Photograph by Liceo Artistico Statale "M. M. Lazzaro" di Catania